

Education Crisis in India: NEP-2020 the new Roadmap! (An insight into Building Academic Leaders for Higher Education Institutions)

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Abstract: What should be the Wisdom of CEO of a Global University? Academic Leadership presently requires a distinct skill to sail through the intricacies of higher education in India. The Higher Education Sector is experiencing gap between scholarly expertise and impactful leadership.

Every institute is unique with its own set of crises, problems, sustainability challenges, solutions, opportunities and prospects of growth & development. Under this dynamic environment what should be the essential fundamental principles of effective leadership in higher institutions in India.

How to design an environment in which innovation influences, diversity impacts, and education accelerates to Global Standards? The question of successfully implementing the “Transformative Leadership Models” is to be still tested in true spirit.

Who will address the scarcity of Academic Leaders in the country? Though we framed NEP-2020, the roadmap for transformation of the education ecosystem, but the shortage of key drivers the Academic Leaders is hindering the navigation of the vision, mission, objectives, and goals as mandated in the reformative policy.

The development of future leaders is also the prime responsibility of the current academic leader. The focus should now shift from the infrastructure to the human structures and system in the Education Institutions/Organizations. The future readiness road map towards India becoming a Global Study Destination is being continually crafted by bringing in innovative restructuring in the India’s Education System. The challenge is how to Globalize the Diverse Education Systems in India? How India can become a hub for Global Education?

India is invariably battling to regain its legacy status of Vishwa Guru. The universally transforming education, learning & teaching is now a subject of Global Quality Standards. The strategy “Internationalization at Home” will open avenues to promote Indian Ethos amidst the Global Culture.

A HEI/University is not a mere information shop, it is a place where one’s intellect, will and emotions are disciplined. Pursuit of knowledge is the soul of the University.

Keywords: Academic Leadership, Empowering Faculty, Succession Planning, Governance System, Higher Education, Vishwa Guru, Internationalization, Global Quality, Indian Ethos, Diverse Education Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Is NEP-2020 the New Roadmap ?Why there is need for Re-defining Indian Universities in India?

The landscape of Academic Leadership in Indian Education System is under transition & transformation through the series of reformations with the enactment of the New Education Policy (NEP-2020).

The major focus is on attaining the standards of Global Higher Education. The philosophy of “Internationalization at Home”will certainly open doors for foreign students but the global challenges in implementation are unending.

India aims to restore its status of being “ A Vishwa Guru”, (Academic Leader) catering to the needs of the Global

Knowledge Society by enforcing the implementation of Academic Leadership Programs all over the country. The recent National Education Policy -2020 by Ministry of Education, Government of India, is a very promising step towards reforming and restructuring by creating Academic Leaders to steer the the Higher Education System in India in line with the Global Standards.

University is a temple of higher learning. Academicians are expected to give up greed and selfishness and work hard with devotion. A true Academic Leader is invariably a seeker of higher knowledge setting aside his personal desires. He has to indulge in higher thinking and work towards noble endeavours.

Will Indian Higher Education Teachers arise to the expectations of the NEP-2020 vision & mandates? The challenge is how to Globalize the Education System in India with orientation of embedded Research. Integrating the diverse education systems for effective interactions will not be free from the mobility of students and scholars from various parts of the Globe.

India's potential towards Learning Environment, Multidisciplinary Education, Quality & Integrity, Motivated & Energized Faculty, Effective Governance & Leadership, Standards for Approvals & Accreditation, Policies & Regulations, Technology Application & Integration, Curriculum & Creativity, Support for Students Professional Career & Growth for transforming the Higher Education System in India; is being put to test for evaluating its Global Standards.

✓ Will the initiatives of NEP-2020 in reforming & restructuring the Higher Education System in India attain the Global outreach?

✓ Will Academic Autonomy to HEIs (Higher Educational Institutions) liberalize, globalize and internationalize the Education System in India?

NEP-2020 is a new vision for institution building in India. Is not the shortage of Academic Leaders impacting the Governance of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)? It is estimated that by 2030, India will have the largest higher education system in the world. There is hardly any correlation between academic qualification and jobs at hand.

Is the education system of yesterday meeting the needs of today? Research is a finer product of higher education leading to innovation and incubation development outcomes for betterment of Society.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

India is home of legendary Leaders (Gurus) like Chanyaka, Tenaliraman, Aryyabhatta, C.V.Raman, Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan, Gautam Buddha, and many more who transformed India setting a benchmark of human capabilities (Leadership) all over the World. In ancient India, Takshashila and University of Nalanda (Nalanda, the seat of knowledge, once lured scholars from abroad like Hiuen Tsang) attracted many scholars from various parts of the globe.

India is proud to witness that many of the Global Corporate houses like Microsoft, Amazon, Google are benefiting from human capabilities nurtured in India .(Indian origin CEO's -holding Global Leadership). We need more and more such Global Leaders to be produced from India.

The National Education Policy 2020 is the first education policy of the 21st Century and aims to address the many growing developmental imperatives of our Country. This Policy proposes the revision and revamping of all aspects of the education structure, including its regulation and governance, to create a new system that is aligned with the aspirational goalsof '21st Century Global Education'; while building upon India's diversified traditions and value systems.

"The Academic Leadership" and "The Internationalization of Higher Education in India", are the major objectives of the New Education Policy. The accelerated rate of Globalization has compelled the Indian policy makers to take immediate measures for transforming the prevailing Higher Education System. The future survival in the Globalized Competitive Economy will demand multidisciplinary, academic leadership capacity building, promoting critical thinking and qualitative skills.

The Multidisciplinary Learning defines that curriculum must include basic arts, crafts, humanities, games, sports and fitness, languages, literature, culture, and values, in addition to science and mathematics, to develop all aspects and capabilities of learners; and make education more well-rounded, useful, and fulfilling to the learner". (NEP-2020).

Moreover, the proposed Global Education System must build character, enable learners to be ethical, rational, compassionate, and caring, amidst diverse cultures while at the same time prepare them for gainful, fulfilling global employment.

The gap between the current state of national learning outcomes and what is required globally must be bridged through undertaking major reforms that bring the highest quality, equity, and integrity into the system, from early childhood care and through higher education.

What are the prime factors responsible for innovating in the present Higher Education System? Though a new 'Global Curriculum' has to be innovated which can synchronize with the NEP-2020 the focus on Academic Leadership cannot be undermined.

One of the key aims of the New Education Policy is Institution Building in Higher Education Sector. To do so HEIs are being encouraged to carry out effective engagement programs for Academic Leaders in India.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this Research through this Case Study is to investigate and understand the essentials of "Why there is critical need for building Academic Leadership to implement Internationalization of Higher Education in India?". Though the constitution for healthy ecosystem for global education in India towards implementing Multidisciplinary Learning & Teaching both at Elementary Schools and Higher Educational Institutions & Universities in India has kicked of the light at the end of the tunnel is yet to be seen in reality.

Moreover, the purpose of the study is also to explore the approaches of our emerging Education System in attaining Academic Leadership to embrace Internationalization of Higher Education in India. The objective is to understand the perspectives on Academic Leadership in the backdrop of "Internationalization of Higher Education" through the concept of Multidisciplinary Learning in India.

India's future readiness & preparedness to become "Vishwa Guru" (Academic Leader) are not free from the apprehensions of global challenges & opportunities. It is a serious concern considering the potential abilities and infrastructural capabilities of the Higher Educational Institutions in India in delivering Global Standards. The Study attempts to examine, "Will the National Education Policy 2020 address the emerging issues of "Institution Building" in India to meet the requirements of Global Study Destination?"

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For which a thorough study of existing literature related to the requirement of Academic Leadership to implement Internationalization of Higher Education in India as well as World has been examined and probed for the essential attributes impacting and influencing the emerging trends in Sustainable Global Education.

The probable major attributes which perhaps are primarily essential to be addressed are Expansion and Excellence, Quality and Quantity, Public & Private, Affordability & Accessibility, Policies and Progress, Governance & Goal, Academic Autonomy and Structures & Systems in the backdrop of Education crises being faced due to Global Policy, Mobility of International Students & Scholars, Leadership of HEIs/University Systems, and Highest Global Standards in Quality Education in making Indian Universities into World Class Global Universities.

The Research design formulated here was to collect primary data on the five (05) broad variables through a structured questionnaire (hard copy & electronic) based on random sampling from the targeted population of Educational Professionals (both Elementary School and Higher Institutions) and Students Community. Understanding the limitations of the study twenty five (25) Education Centers each (i.e., a mix of major Schools, Colleges and Higher Educational Institutions /Universities) across India, was specifically focused, examined and considered for ten (10) respondents from each Education Centre.

In total the field responses of two hundred fifty (250, @10 each from scattered (25) Higher Education Institutions/Universities/Centres across India) respondents were recorded, examined, evaluated and analyzed co-relating with the secondary data sourced from literature review for understanding the emerging trends in Academic Leadership, Governance System and Capacity Building of India's Higher Education System; with respect to Gap Analysis on existing potentials and capabilities the Higher Educational Institutions have in imparting Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Curriculum for international students and Creativity in Global Higher Educational Courses. Based on these findings through Quantitative Analysis using simple descriptive statistical tools of percentage the Researcher has recommended and suggested valuable remedial measures and initiatives for developing Academic Leadership in India.

Problem Statements

- ✓ Can India's Education crisis be eliminated by 2030?
- ✓ Will India become Home to Foreign Students?
- ✓ Do we have Academic Leadership in place to make the scheme "Internationalization of Home" successful?
- ✓ Will the initiative of "Institution Building in India" by "NEP-2020" create a holistic Global Education System?
- ✓ Is the rate of revamping "Structures & Systems" satisfactory in HEIs?

To evaluate India's presently emerging Global Higher Education System suffering with dual policies, processes, teaching & learning experiences, effectiveness, objectives, outcomes and impacts following attributes as variables have been designed for study as Problem Statements in the present Research in the backdrop of the major initiatives undertaken by University Grants Commission (UGC) which is a statutory body under Ministry of Education, Government of India, entrusted with the task of determination, coordination and maintenance of standards of teaching, examination and research in University Education, in regulations, guidelines, amendments and recommended establishments for successful implementation of NEP-2020.

1. Expansion and Excellence

Do we really understand Academic Freedom? It is time when both the expansion and excellence of higher education institutions or universities are needed to escalate the literacy rate in India.

One remarkable focus of this research study is that the Academic Leaders lack professional Managerial know-how to operate Institutions as Enterprises or Business Organizations.

Every Teacher is to be made accountable like the Manager in the Business Organization. Only banking on the National perspectives narrows the overall understanding of the Global Education environment.

There has been a tremendous increase in the number of higher educational institutes in the country. Therefore the Academic Leadership programs are essential to transform the traditional traits into hybrid models. It is more about the utilization and efficiency of resources rather than individual's performance. The focus is to be on group and integrated achievement.

Do we have a Global Policy on expansion and excellence of Higher Education System in India? It is to understand that there is true necessity to adapt and adopt paradigm shift in synergy of cultures, behaviour, morals, ethics, values and perceptions among the students preparing to become Global Citizens.

2. Quality and Quantity

Highest Global Standards in Quality Education is not a distant dream if the Academic Leadership program takes off. Though implementation of NEP-2020 promises to attain the highest global standards in Quality Education but the prevailing governance system is not fulfilling the desired expectations the policy had envisaged. The NEP -2020 so far has not been successful in synchronizing & integrating the National & Global Policies in Higher Education.

- ✓ Is India's Higher Education System capable of transforming Indian Universities to World Class Universities?
- ✓ Is India prepared for technological up-gradation to overcome the higher educational disruptions in the World?
- ✓ Can Academic Leadership programs help in attracting and managing mobility of International Students & Scholars?

The NEP-2020 talks about both Nationalization (Atam Nirbhar Bharat) and Internationalization (Globalization). A new 'Education Mix' is emerging in India redefining the landscape of Academic Leadership.

3. Governance and Goal

Moreover the political interference in the governance of Universities, like appointments of Vice-Chancellors still persists questioning the academic freedom. When it comes to the discharging of dual responsibilities by switching of role of the honourable Governor (being the head of State) to Chancellor (the head of University) of Universities in the State, under the belt of his excellency, the functions and decision making is still buried in the bureaucratic legacy of political governance.

Similar is the matter when President of India acts on the aid and advice of the council of ministers, though the role is of the Visitor of a higher education institution or a university. The regulations need to clearly demarcate the differences between Constitutional Framework and the Academic Framework.

Though we had several discourses on the governance of HEIs still the practicing framework could not be justified. The future of Indian Universities without doubt is in the hands of Academic Leaders.

The “Academic Goals” should rise above the “Political Goals” in the country. The Institutions of higher learning have been used as instruments for political motives in India hampering the academic achievements of students.

India is lacking Institutional Leadership. The focus is on HEI’s becoming independent Self-Governing Institutions pursuing innovation & excellence. Unless the Indian Academic System thinks qualitatively with the perfect Governing System perception the future readiness will be incomplete with respect to Global Standards.

This Research Paper is an insightful examination of a much awaited issue of the higher education in India.

4. Public & Private

Is not HEIs in the Private Sector partners to the Public Sector? How can the same regulations be applicable to both Public and Private Higher Institutions in India? The Autonomous Institutions have their governing system more of compliance type rather than bureaucratic type as the public institutions follow.

The ‘Autonomous Higher Education Institutions’ providing freedom to student’s “Choice of Course” with the option of “Multiple entries and exit points” being introduced through the establishment of “Academic Bank of Credit”, as per the NEP-2020 is incomplete without Academic Leaders .

The right competencies and capabilities for Academic Leadership in India is still being mapped. The transformation of ‘Traditional Values’ into ‘Global Values’ should be the pledge of all stakeholders of the Internationalization programme.

5. Affordability and Accessibility

In addition to the competition in providing Premium Education at affordable cost the accessibility is another major factor for Higher Education in India.

Is our NEP-2020 focusing on the Internationalization of Higher Education? Though NEP-2020 has initiated the “Transforming Education through the integration of Technology”, Pupil Teacher Ratio (PTR), SWAYAM/MOOC, the creation of the National Educational Technological Forum (NETF) and National Research Foundation (NRF), the three cardinal principles of India’s New Educational Policy- Access, Equity and Quality, still lot is to be done for the Global Educational framework.

V. ANALYSIS, FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

The (field & virtual) survey was carried out with the help of both (hard copy & electronic) questionnaires respectively and the selective respondents on sampling were interviewed (both in field & through google meet mode/telephonically) for their views on the area of Research related to “ Education Crisis in India”.

Based on their opinions and feedback the data was analyzed and accordingly outcomes have been worked out. The findings were then mapped with the secondary data available from the relevant review of literature in the area of study. And it was interpreted to understand the perspectives of Educational Professionals on the Academic Leadership in India’s Higher Education System along with the gaps in the emerging trends mandated in NEP-2020; after analyzing both the primary and secondary data.

Demographic Information Gathered

The Survey revealed that the gender responses; male is to female ratio was 60% to 40%. In Age Group category it was observed as 27.5% under 25 years, 36.5% for 26-35 years, 18.0% for 36-45 years, 9.0% for 46-55 years and 9.0% for above 56 years. The responses for period of service (years) in Education Sector were distributed as 18.2% for <5, 9.1% for >5, 9.1% for <10, 27.3% for >10 <15, 18.2% for >15<20 and 18.2% for >25 years. For the Relationship Status of the Individual respondents following can be summarized; 18.2% were unmarried, 70 % were married and 11.8% were found to be divorced/separated. The type of family of the respondents was 27.3% for Joint and 72.7% for Nuclear.

The distribution in the Higher Teacher Category who participated in the Research Survey was 9.1% for University Professor, 9.1% for Teachers from Higher Institutions, 45.4% for Teachers as Administrators (dual responsibility), 16.4% for Private Teachers, 10% for Education Consultants (attached with HEIs/Universities), and 10% for non-Teaching (Pure Administrators).

Interpretation

1. Do you understand the meaning of “Academic Leadership” by “NEP-2020” in India? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
2. Are we ready with a sound legal framework for Academic Leadership Program in India? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
3. Are our Academic Leaders prepared for Global Education Pedagogy? 32.3 % of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 4.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
4. Will the objective of “Education for All” in Higher Education be achieved by 2035? 32.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 17.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
5. Perspective on, “The NEP-2020 talks dual; about both Nationalization (Atam Nirbhar Bharat) and Internationalization (Globalization)”. 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
6. Is India’s Education System getting Globalized, Commercialized and Corporatized? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
7. Is India prepared for the human resources up-gradation to overcome the global educational disruptions in the World? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
8. Will all the higher learning Institutions be converted into International Institutions by 2040? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
9. Are you in favor of opening an International Student’s Office at your HEI/ University? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
10. Can globalizing the Academic Governance System help in developing all capabilities of Institutions to meet the challenges of the 21st Century? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
11. What is your opinion on the “Is India’s Higher Education System capable of attracting and managing mobility of International Students & Scholars?”, as per the NEP-2020? 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
12. Do we have Global Academic Leaders in India? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
13. Your opinion on, “Is Institution Building in India a step for transforming the entire ecosystem of higher education in India? ”. 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
14. Can India provide Premium Education at affordable cost? 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
15. Will Academic Leadership thrust by NEP-2020 raise the Global Standards of Quality in Higher Education in India?

27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.

16. Will “ ‘GLOBAL SKILL’ Education replace Vocational Education in India”? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
17. Comment on, “Efficiency in utilizing & interfacing the resources of HEIs/University Systems”.. 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
18. Is our NEP-2020 focusing on the Governing System of Higher Education? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
19. Do we have a Global Policy on “Affordability and Accessibility” which would help to achieve the targets and mandates of NEP-2020? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
20. Share your opinion on the, “India’s future readiness & preparedness for future Academic Leaders is not free from the apprehensions of global challenges & opportunities”. 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
21. Will Collaborative Academic Leadership program improve Global Teaching & Learning? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
22. Your comment on, “Do we really understand “Academic Freedom” in Higher Education in India?” 32.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 5.1% of the respondents Disagree and 4 % Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 17.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
23. For the dimension, “Are the Academic Administrators” ensuring that universities do not waver from their goals and aspirations? . 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 14.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 17.2% had no opinion to share.
24. Opinion on, “Quantity & Quality of Academic Leaders in India”. 27.3% of the total sample respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree that quality of Academic Leaders training has improved in India, 19.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 7.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
25. Will the NEP-2020 bring better accreditation for Global Quality Education? 37.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 4.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the rest 17.2% remained Neutral without sharing their opinion on the above problem statement. The Researcher discovered that a whopping majority nearly 74% agreed that NEP -2020 can bring accreditation for Quality Education in India. This finding is very much in line with the purpose with which the NEP-2020 had been initiated by India’s Educational Policy Makers.
26. Will Education Excellence platform achieve the three cardinal principles of India’s New Educational Policy, Access, Equity and Quality? 32.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% of the respondents each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 17.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
27. Is NEP-2020 the right roadmap for integrating “Locally, Nationally, Internationally” ? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
28. For the dimension Opinion on, “The role of Visitor (Governor and President as Chancellors of Universities) in relation to HEIs across the country needs to be redefined aligning with Internationalization Strategies in context with the National Education Policies”. 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
29. For the dimension, “Will incentivizing teachers improve the performance of the Academic Leaders in Indian Higher Education System?”, 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 36.4% remained Neutral, 4% Disagree

and 5% Strongly Disagree. It is healthy to note the researcher's discovery that nearly 54% majority of the respondents have faith that incentivizing teachers will certainly improve the performance of the Academic Leaders in Indian Higher Education System.

30. Will the implementation of NEP-2020 improve collaboration between Indian Universities and Foreign Universities? For this problem statement, 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% of respondents each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the rest 9% remained Neutral.

Suggestion -Way Forward

Is NEP-2020 the future roadmap? Is certainly the promising hope as reported by the respondents from the higher education sector in India.

“Education Crisis in India” can certainly be resolved as mandated by the Ministry of India. The focus on ‘India a Global Study Destination’ is attainable only through the campaign drive of Academic Leadership Programs in HEIs.

Though the Indian Higher Education System has started thinking qualitatively with the Internationalization perception for Sustainable Global Educational Growth & Development the inappreciable enrolment of students in higher research is a major concern.

The future readiness is only through developing more and more Academic Leaders through out the country. Though the ultimate aim of Internationalization of Learning & Higher Education is to prepare Students for a Sustainable-Global Knowledge Society the dream can only be fulfilled by promoting Academic Leadership and improving Governance System in higher educational institutions in India.

VI. CONCLUSION

Policy initiatives in higher education in India have been shaped by various commissions and committees ranging from the Kothari Commission (1966), the Rashtriya Uchcharat Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA-2013) to the latest National Education Policy (new NEP-2020).

The future of Indian higher education will significantly depend upon the ability to provide transformative (Academic Leadership) in every aspect of institution building.

Today, Higher Education is not only the cornerstone in the foundation of Nation Building but equally responsible for Global Building and it is only possible through Institution Building.

The Academic Leadership Program is being emphasized to meet India's aim of becoming ‘Global Education Hub’. Thus, in the pursuit of Internationalization -Teaching & Learning our Academic Governing System must create enabling environment for continual opportunities to attract international students, academics, researchers and teachers from numerous subject areas and faculty across the Globe.

Indian Higher Education should move towards more incubation centres, innovations and research beyond academic limitations. Academic Leaders have to start learning to think critically and solve emerging problems globally. The question is, how to be creative and multidisciplinary, and how to innovate, adapt, and absorb new material in novel and changing fields.

A great country should have great Universities. The ambitious goal of raising higher education in India from its current state of mediocrity to world-class standards of excellence is dream to be realized before 2047, when India celebrates 100 years of Independence.

Capacity Building should be in line with , “The Global Pedagogy” (A New Education Mix) which is evolving to make Higher Education more enthusiastic, experiential, holistic, multidisciplinary integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented, learner-centered, discussion-based, flexible, and, of course, enjoyable.

It is not only the “Collaboration of Global Technologies” but even the “Collaboration of Global Cultures” is equally to be addressed by the Indian Higher Education System striving to Globalize through the philosophy of Internationalization. At present the investments in Internationalization programme has been not much brainstormed and channelized for successful implementation in India.

The pursuance of NEP-2020 is promisingly going to improve and attain the objectives of GER, PTR, VET, SWAYAM, MOOC and Global Citizens giving a new global outlook to India's Higher Education.

Moreover though the policy of commercialization & corporatization have been criticized; the mandate of “Access, Equity and Quality” is certainly going to revolutionize the overall supply chain and transform India’s Higher Education System to attain “Internationalization at Home”.

India was a Vishwa Guru (Academic Leader-The Seat of Knowledge) and will certainly continue with its legacy remaining a Vishwa Guru.

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